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MODELING BASIC NOISE INDICATORS OF ENVIRONMENTAL NOISE FOR THE PERIOD 1985 - 2010

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Abstract - Noise is recognized as a physical hazard in the environment, it causes adverse effects to human health and it is also potentially harmful form of energy in the environment. Although the hazards and the risks to human health from noise are generally much higher in the occupational, however, the exposure of the entire population to the different frequencies environmental noise for a long time, leads to population health impairments, which is in the field of the research of medical ecology. The noise measurement results in the City of Novi Sad (NS) since 1985, show that the environmental noise, dominated from road traffic, is a long-lasting physical hazard. Since 2011, the experts from the Public Health Institute of Vojvodina (IZJZV) conduct 24-hour outdoor environmental noise measurements and directly determine the values of basic noise indicators (L_{day} , $L_{evening}$, L_{night} , L_{den}). In order to examine the environmental noise as a physical hazard and in order to determine the percentage of the population annoyed by noise for a long time, based on the 387 analyzed 24-hour noise measurements in the period 2011-2016, using linear regression, in this paper we established the predictive equations for determining the basic noise indicators. The equations are used in the purpose of modeling the basic noise indicators for the period 1985-1990. For that time period, IZJZV possess the equivalent noise levels (L_{Aeq}) from a series of 15-minute measurements. Using this approach of modeling, we achieve the quality insight into the environmental noise levels and the population annoyance by the noise in the NS for a period of three decades.

1. INTRODUCTION AND THE AIM OF THE WORK

1.1 Introduction

The environmental noise is, due to European Noise Directive (END), unwanted / harmful outdoor sound created by human activities, including noise emitted by means of transport, road traffic, rail traffic, air traffic, and from sites of industrial activity [1]. Except it is subjectively disagreeable, noise is recognized as a physical hazard from environment, it causes adverse effects to human health and it is also potentially harmful form of energy in the environment. Although the hazards and the risks to human health are generally much higher in the occupational [2], however, the exposure of the

entire population to the different frequencies environmental noise for a long time, leads to population health impairments, which is in the field of the medical ecology research. The noise effect on humans depends on many factors - noise level, duration, frequency, variability over the time, time when a man is exposed (day, evening, night), individual sensitivity, health condition and mental health. The basic classification of noise effects on humans is: the effect on the hearing system - the auditory effect of noise and the effect on other organs and organic systems - the extraauditive noise effect.

According to contemporary scientific insights of the World Health Organization (WHO), the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), environmental noise is recognized as a factor that leads to anxiety, hearing impairments, sleep disturbance, cognitive disorders in children and cardiovascular diseases. The environmental noise is, also, a stressogenic factor that affects human mental health as well [3].

Noise makes difficult to people perform complex tasks, change their social behavior and cause annoyance. The noise is a psychosocial stressor and activates the sympathetic and endocrine system [4]. During the response to stress, the hormonal system of hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis is activated. That results in increased secretion of catecholamines, such as adrenaline, and corticosteroids, such as cortisol. This hormonal imbalance, speeds up heart rate and increases the blood pressure, also affects many other metabolic processes in the body. Therefore, noise is recognized as a risk factor for myocardial infarction, because it is a stressor, activating the hormone system, also, noise potentiates the most significant risk factors for this myocardial infarction, such is an arterial hypertension [5].

Exposed to noise, people are annoyed and disturbed. Introverts had more pronounced subjective effects of annoyance, poor concentration and fatigue during mental performance in noise compared to quiet conditions [6]. Residents living in the neighborhood of the airports and noisy streets are frequently complained of headache, and have a feeling of tension and tiredness. High levels of aircraft noise were associated with increased risks of stroke, coronary heart disease, and cardiovascular disease for both hospital admissions and mortality in areas near large airports [7].

The studies showed that respondents from noisy area significantly more often reported difficulty in falling asleep, being woken up, poor sleep quality, tiredness after sleep, and use of sleep medication than residents from quiet areas. The sleep disturbance is the major health effect of urban environmental noise. Also, it is known that noise may restrict the use of parts of the house, prevent windows or doors from being opened, and cause distraction when reading, writing, or having a conversation [8, 9].

WHO estimates, in total, the number of deaths linked to the unhealthy environments amounts to 12.6 million per year (based on 2012 data). WHO also estimates that 23% of global deaths are due to environmental factors [10]. Results indicate that at least one million healthy life years are lost every year from traffic related noise in the western part of Europe (DALYs - disability-adjusted life-years) [11]. For the City of Belgrade, it is estimated that total DALY due to road traffic noise equals 107 years / million inhabitants [12].

Based on one published research, daytime traffic noise affects heart diseases in 3% of all heart disease cases, night time background noise causes sleep disturbance in 2% of all Europeans, total noise causes annoyance of 15% of all Europeans, traffic noise causes 3% of all tinnitus cases, daytime and night-time noise leads to slower learning by children in 0,01%, and, also, loud music causes in hearing loss from "leisure noise" in 1,8% of 7 to 19 year olds in Europe [13].

In one Serbian cross sectional interview study, it is showed that highly noise disturbed adult male residents were under increased risk of arterial hypertension and myocardial infarction, compared to subjects slightly annoyed, or not annoyed by noise [14]. During 2006, the average daytime noise of 69 dB in the City of Novi Sad was a contributing factor to the burden of ischemic heart diseases in 14% of cases [15]. Another study has identified the presence of public transport at daytime and at night as a significant and independent predictor of high noise annoyance [16].

Recent studies on long term noise exposure, especially night noise ≥ 55 dB, have reported relationship with pathogenesis of male infertility. Large epidemiological studies on community noise have reported its relationship with breast cancer, stroke, type 2 diabetes, and obesity [17]. Further research is needed to examine coping strategies and possible health consequences of adaptation to noise [18].

1.2 The aim of this work

The aim of this paper is to show the model of using historical data on environmental noise measurements. These data can be used for modeling basic noise indicators. Using this approach of modeling, we achieve the quality insight into the environmental noise levels, and also into the population annoyance by noise for a period of three decades. These approach shows that the environmental noise, dominated from road traffic, is a long-lasting physical hazard in the urban city of Novi Sad.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Environmental noise measurements in Novi Sad for the time period 1985- 2010

The city of Novi Sad is the largest city in the AP Vojvodina. The City is administrative, cultural, scientific, medical, university and political center center, while 300.000 of people is exposed to the environmental noise levels shown in this paper.

Public Health Institute of Vojvodina (IZJZV) possess an environmental noise data since 1985, to the present day. For the time period 1985 - 2010, data are available in the form of average daily / monthly / annual equivalent noise levels (L_{eq})

The oldest available reports in the archives of the IZJZV about measuring environmental noise in Novi Sad date from April 1985. Since 1985, environmental noise measurements were carried out each month in three day intervals (06:30, 14:00, 17:00) on two measuring sites in the course of a single day. Night-time measurements were conducted in two intervals (0:30, 03:30) on all measuring sites where day-time measurements were done. With minor changes, this methodology was maintained until 2011. Ever since then, 24-hour measurements have been conducted. At all times, noise measurements were accompanied by counting number of vehicles on the streets, and, also, measuring of microclimatic parameters.

In regard to equipment used for measuring noise levels, records show that in the period 1985 – 1989 the Noise level meter Type 2205 by Brüel and Kjær was used, from 1990 to 2002, the Brüel&Kjær 4427 was used, from 2002 to 2009 the Brüel & Kjær 2260 Investigator was used with the 4231 type calibrator, condenser microphone type 4189 and the Software Noise Explorer Type 7815 Version 4.15.

Since April 2009, the IZJZV has been using a system which consists of: The Brüel&Kjær Noise meter type 2250, Brüel&Kjær type 3535-A (a protective case that acts as physical protection equipment), Brüel&Kjær Outdoor Microphone type 4952, BZ 5503 Utility Software and the Noise Explorer Type 7815 Software.

From 1985 to 2017, environmental noise in the City of Novi Sad was measured at more than forty measuring sites. Measuring sites have been changed in time, because of the request of city administration or because of technical problems (equipment safety, availability of electricity, works under construction...)

2.2 Methodology of modeling basic noise indicators for the time period 1985- 2010

In order to examine the environmental noise as a long-lasting physical hazard, also in order to identify the percentage of population annoyed by noise, we established the predictive equations for modeling basic noise indicators (L_{day} , L_{night} , $L_{evening}$, L_{den}). We analyzed 387 24-hour noise measurements from the latest period (2011-2016), and established the predictive equations applying the linear regression. The equations are used in the purpose of modeling the basic noise indicators for the period 1985-1990. For that time period, IZJZV possess the equivalent noise levels (L_{Aeq}) from a series of 15-minute measurements. Using this approach of modeling, we achieve the quality insight into the environmental noise levels and the population annoyance by the noise in the city for a period of three decades.

The established predictive equations are:

$$L_{day} = L_{Aeq} \cdot 1,003 + 1,110$$

$$L_{evening} = L_{Aeq} \cdot 0,949 + 2,820$$

$$L_{night} = L_{Aeq} \cdot 0,993 - 3,718$$

Coefficients of determination for the given equations is: $R^2=0,96$ for L_{day} equations ; $R^2=0,63$ for $L_{evening}$ and $R^2=0,67$ for L_{night} .

Note: L_{den} is calculated from the modeled basic noise indicators using the standard equation:

$$L_{den} = 10 \lg \left[\frac{1}{24h} (t_{day} \cdot 10^{0,1L_{day,12}} + t_{evening} \cdot 10^{0,1(L_{evening,4+5dB})} + t_{night} \cdot 10^{0,1(L_{night,8+10dB})}) \right] dB$$

3. RESULTS

This paper shows measured annual equivalent noise levels (L_{eq}), and then the modeled values of the basic noise indicators for one representative measuring site used in 1985 - 2010, "Novo Naselje" in Novi Sad.

The position of the measuring point within the "Novo Naselje" has been moved during decades (the reasons are City administration demands, and also technical issues, electricity, works under construction). For that reason, only shown data in this paper are for the year when the measuring point was located near "the Stoteks store" at Jovan Dučić Boulevard, or closer to the corner of Boulevard Jovan Dučić and Bate Brkić Street (Table 1).

Fig. 1 Historical photo, measuring site "Novi Naselje" in 2009, Novi Sad / View to the corner of Jovan Ducic Boulevard and Bate Brkić Street

Table 1 Measured annual equivalent noise levels (L_{eq}) and modeled values of the basic noise indicators for one representative measuring site used in 1985 - 2010, "Novo Naselje" in Novi Sad

Year	Measured values / dB	Modeled values of the basic noise indicators / dB			
	* Annual equivalent noise levels (L_{eq})	L_{day}	$L_{evening}$	L_{night}	L_{den}
1985	69,0	70,3	68,3	64,8	72,8
1986	69,0	70,3	68,3	64,8	72,8
1987	68,0	69,3	67,4	63,8	71,8
1988	68,2	69,5	67,5	64,0	72,0
1989	69,1	70,4	68,4	64,9	72,9
1990	-	-	-	-	-
1991	-	-	-	-	-
1992	-	-	-	-	-
1993	-	-	-	-	-
1994	-	-	-	-	-
1995	69,0	70,3	68,3	64,8	72,8
1996	60,0	61,3	59,8	55,9	63,9
1997	62,0	63,3	61,7	57,8	65,9
1998	66,0	67,3	65,5	61,8	69,8
1999	63,0	64,3	62,6	58,8	66,9
2000	64,0	65,3	63,6	59,8	67,9
2001	65,0	66,3	64,5	60,8	68,8
2002	63,0	64,3	62,6	58,8	66,9
2003	61,0	62,3	60,7	56,9	64,9
2004	63,0	64,3	62,6	58,8	66,9
2005	62,3	63,6	61,9	58,1	66,2
2006	-	-	-	-	-
2007	-	-	-	-	-
2008	64,9	66,2	64,4	60,7	68,7
2009	65,5	66,8	65,0	61,3	69,3
2010	64,6	65,9	64,1	60,4	68,4

* Sources of data: IZJZV reports for the period 1985 - 2010

Note: the environment noise in the City of Novi Sad, the subject of this paper, is the road traffic noise. There are no data about railway noise or air traffic noise in Novi Sad - Novi Sad has no airport, also, rail traffic is not monitored, the railroad does not pass through parts of the city covered by environmental noise monitoring network.

The Serbian national norm from 2010 [19] prescribes the equation for calculating the percentage of highly annoyed population (% HA) by road traffic noise.

$$\% \text{ HA} = 9.868 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot (L_{\text{den}} - 42)^3 - 1.436 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot (L_{\text{den}} - 42)^2 + 0.5118 \cdot (L_{\text{den}} - 42)$$

Based on modeled data from previous decades, it is assessment that highly annoyed population percentage (%HA) by road traffic noise in "Novo Naselje", Novi Sad, for time period 1985 - 2010, is in the range 16 - 31% (table 2).

Table 2 The assessment of highly annoyed population percentage (% HA) by road traffic noise in "Novo Naselje", Novi Sad, 1985 - 2010

Year	Modeled values / dB / L_{den}	Highly annoyed population percentage (%HA)
1985	72,8	31
1986	72,8	31
1987	71,8	29
1988	72,0	29
1989	72,9	31
1990	-	-
1991	-	-
1992	-	-
1993	-	-
1994	-	-
1995	72,8	31
1996	63,9	15
1997	65,9	18
1998	69,8	24
1999	66,9	19
2000	67,9	21
2001	68,8	22
2002	66,9	19
2003	64,9	16
2004	66,9	19
2005	66,2	18
2006	-	-
2007	-	-
2008	68,7	22
2009	69,3	23
2010	68,4	22

4. DISCUSSION

The possibility of using these predictive equations for modeling basic noise indicators (L_{day} , L_{evening} , L_{night} , L_{den}) should be examined on the example of some other noise data from some other communities.

Once again, it should be noted, the predictive equations were established applying the linear regression, using analyzed 387

24-hour noise measurements from the latest period (2011-2016), and variability of L_{day} can be explained by this equation in 96% of cases, and variability L_{evening} and L_{night} in two thirds of cases (relative to the L_{eq} in the 24-hour period). However, the one model that can predict every possible scenario with 100% security - does not exist. Therefore, this model can be improved. Different predictive equations can be established, e.g. for the measured noise levels (L_{eq}) in the ranges of 50-55dB, 55-60 dB, 60-65 dB, 65-70 dB and > 70 dB. Of course, all of this can be done if there exists a need for better processing of historical data.

This paper presents that highly annoyed population percentage (%HA) by road traffic noise in "Novo Naselje", Novi Sad, for time period 1985 - 2010, is in the range 16 - 31%.

In relation to measured average five-year L_{den} in city zones, according to urban use of the space in the City of Novi Sad, during the 2012-2016, %HA was 11% in "residential areas", 21% in "city center and city traffic", 18% in "recreation areas and hospital areas" and 25% in "business and residential areas". Therefore, in representative zones of the City of Novi Sad, %HA was in the range 11 - 25% [20].

The higher values of noise levels during the 1980s and 1990s, compared to the values from the last decade at the same measuring points in the City of Novi Sad, can also be interpreted from the aspect of used different measurement equipment and different methodologies.

Also, historical data show that minimum and maximum values of the noise level are approaching to each other. This indicates that the noise in the city is more and more "equally distributed" and presented everywhere. This was demonstrated by professional papers from IZJZV [21,22].

5. CONCLUSION

The predictive equations for modeling basic noise indicators (L_{day} , L_{evening} , L_{night} , L_{den}) can be useful model for other cities and institutions which possess historical environment noise data.

In this way, historical data can be analyzed in a modern way, and can also be used for other purposes, for example, making noise maps.

The data presented in this paper examine the environmental noise as a long-lasting physical hazard.

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